

LNGA MCHOD 'GANDEN OFFERING OF THE TWENTY-FIFTH DAY' IN MDO BA (DUOWA), THUN RIN (REB GONG, TONGREN) CITY, MTHO SNGON (QINGHAI) PROVINCE, PR CHINA

Pad+ma rig 'dzin བུ་དྲུ་རིག་འཛོལ། (Wanmarenzeng 完么仁增)

ABSTRACT

The history of Mdo ba (Duowa) Monastery, an introduction to Dga' ldan lnga mchod¹ 'Ganden Offering of the Twenty-Fifth Day' and its rituals practiced in the monastery and local communities, and a model for recording and preserving endangered religious activities, cultural practices, social gatherings, and traditions in a rapidly changing society are given in the context of Mdo ba Town, Thun rin (Reb gong, Tongren) City, Mtho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China.

KEYWORDS

Dga' ldan lnga mchod, *ganden ngamchoe*, *lnga mchod*, Mdo ba (Duowa), Mtho sngon (Qinghai), Thun rin (Reb gong), Tibetan cultural preservation

INTRODUCTION

Mdo ba 'brog dgon pa mdo sngags dar rgyas gling 'The Secluded Monastery of Mdo ba: the Sutra and Mantra Propagation Center' is in the lap of a hill above Mdo ba Township Town, ninety-seven kilometers east of Reb gong (Thun rin, Tongren) Town. Monks lived in black yak-hair tents around 1915 and earlier and moved

¹ Names for this festival in English include Butter Lamp Festival, which may be a translation of the Chinese term Randeng jie 燃灯节. The Tibetan name is known as Ganden Ngamchoe. In this article, I will refer to it as Lnga mchod, a short form for Dga' ldan lnga mchod. This short form is the term locals most often use.

seasonally with Mdo ba nomadic families. At this time, locals referred to the monastery as Ra sgar 'Black Yak-hair Tent Monastery'. Gcod le (1937-2024) recalled:

Because of thievery, robbing, and invasions from communities outside Mdo ba, Ra sgar had no permanent location and followed Mdo ba families seasonally from winter pasture to summer pasture, then from autumn pasture to winter pasture. Later, monks dug pits inside their tents and settled about five kilometers west of [the contemporary] Mdo ba Town Center, known as Klad rko. The pits were warm and neat. During this time, monks living in black yak-hair tents didn't observe strict discipline like contemporary monks. In my childhood, monks wore *wa gor* 'fox-fur hats' during winter.

Nian and Bai (1993:164) reported 1915 as Ra sgar's founding.² In 1954, the tenth PaN chen Bla ma (1938-1989) chose the location of Mdo ba Monastery through divination. Locals built adobe temples the next year. Until 1958, there was an Assembly Hall and a Protector Hall with around eighty rooms and a total of about 600 rooms in thirty courtyards for monks in an area of 19.2 mu.³ There were sixty monks in the monastery. The monastery had 500 horses, 3,000 yaks, and 6,000 sheep and re-opened for religious activities in June 1987. Dge 'dun rgya mtsho (1904-?) managed all monastic events from 1954 to 1958.

Sman tog (b. 1929-1990) was a local monk and monastery manager in the 1990s. There were thirty-six monks in Mdo ba Monastery in 1991, of whom thirty-four had recently become monks. Four had attended the local primary school. Rebuilding an

² It is likely there was a community of religious practitioners including the Sa skya, Bka' gyud, and Bka' gdams schools; and Tantric and Bon practitioners, but I have found no resources to support this.

³ A Chinese *mu* equals 0.067 hectares.

Assembly Hall with twenty rooms, a *nang chen*⁴ (FIGS. 11-1;2) with ninety-one rooms, and about thirty rooms in six courtyards for monks took place in the 1990s.

According to Reb gong pa 'jigs med bsam grub (2013:528-33) and Ri khrod pa dge 'dun bstan pa (nd:182-184), local monk Dge 'dun rgya mtsho (born in Khyi rnga Community) received a *dge bshes* degree from Bla brang Monastery,⁵ returned home, and began building new monastery buildings for monks living in Ra sgar in 1956. The eighty monks in the monastery began observing strict monastic discipline entailing the study and memorization of scriptures. They were also forbidden to leave the monastery without permission from the disciplinarian, and participation in chanting in the assembly hall was required.

The Peaceful Liberation of Tibet (Xizang, TAR 1951) and the Cultural Revolution (1966-1976) disrupted religious practice in Mdo ba Monastery from 1958 to 1980 with monks becoming laymen. Dge 'dun rgya mtsho did not return home after imprisonment, and locals lost contact with him.

⁴ A *bla ma's* house. His monk assistants typically run the house, receive guests and manage the *bla ma's* property.

⁵ Bla brang Monastery is located in nearby Xiahe County, Kan su'u (Gansu) Province.

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In 1981, Skal bzang bstan 'dzin⁶ (1929-1990) and Brtson 'grus⁷ (1923-2001) began rebuilding Mdo ba Monastery, constructed a new twelve-*gyan*⁸ sized temple (FIG. 9) that held several *sman sku*⁹ of Tsong kha pa (1357-1419), (see FIG. 10-5) Rgyal tshab dar ma rin chen (1364-1432),¹⁰ and Mkhas grub dge

⁶ Known locally as Sman tog (1929-1990), he was born in Kha skya Community, took monastic vows at the age of eight, lived in Mdo ba Monastery until he was nineteen, and then studied Buddhist scriptures and Tibetan medicine at Rong bo Monastery. He worked in the Tibetan Medicine Hospital of Rma lho (Huangnan) in 1967 and as a *rkang rjen sman pa* 'barefoot doctor' in 1969. In 1981, he assumed responsibility for rebuilding Mdo ba Monastery, completed in 1985. In the following year, he donated his medicines and medical instruments to the monastery. He began building a clinic benefitting residents and patients from Rtse khog (Zeku) and the Bla brang (Xiahe) areas. See the online article by the Tibetan Medicine Hospital, Rongwo Monastery (https://mp.weixin.qq.com/s?__biz=MzkwMjY1OTQzNg==&mid=2247487368&idx=2&sn=6c826f9a21ca61f9ccbcbabb1083c894&source=41#w_echat_redirect, accessed 11 August 2024).

⁷ Local monk, Lhag bsam (b. 1968) said:

Brtson 'grus was born in Khyi Inga and was the brother of Tshe dpa's (b. 1963) mother (Sgrol dkar, b. 1937). He and Sman tog were the only monks among seventy to eighty who kept their vows during the Cultural Revolution. Btson 'grus was a knowledgeable monk. During the Cultural Revolution he was a *zhwa gon* 'person wearing a hat' [certain Cultural Revolution victims were forced to wear paper 'dunce' hats while they were criticized in front of a crowd] and worked serving Mdo ba Township officers making bridles, saddle blankets, pads, and so on. He contributed his life and skills to rebuilding the monastery after it was reopened, along with the highly respected monk physician, Sman tog.

⁸ One *gyan* equals about fifteen square meters.

⁹ Images made of gold, silver, copper, iron, brass, and zinc - six medicinal metals.

¹⁰ Tsong kha pa's student, the first Dga' ldan khri pa 'Goden Throne Holder' of the Dge lugs tradition after Tsong kha pa's death, and a prolific writer (<https://encyclopediaofbuddhism.org/wiki/Gelug>, accessed 12 August 2024).

legs dpal bzang¹¹ (1385-1438); a wall painting of *lam rim tshogs zhing*;¹² and scriptures including the *Bka' 'gyur* and *Bstan 'gyur*. Afterward, the number of monastery monks gradually increased in number.

...

According to locals, the container for burning a butter lamp is a *rkong bu* or *mchod rkong*. However, people usually refer to the cup according to its material. If the cup is made of silver or brass, it is called *dnqul rkong* or *zangs rkong*. A *phye rkong* is a cup made of wheat flour dough (my translation: 'dough-ghee burner') that is offered during the night of the Lnga mchod on the twenty-fifth day of the tenth lunisolar month, commemorating Tsong kha pa's nirvana.

This is the scene of offering countless butter lamps on both roofs and yards of temples on the night of Tsong kha pa's nirvana, according to the most well-known biography of the master by his close disciple Mkhas grub dge legs dpal bzang (1385-1438), the third abbot of Dga' ldan Monastery:

At that time, countless butter lamps were offered in the direction of or facing the master's chapel on the roof eaves of the monastery's rooms.

¹¹ Born in Central TAR (Xizang), he took novice ordination at the age of seven and became one of Tsong kha pa's most devoted disciples in 1407. In 1431, he assumed the Golden Throne. He died in 1438 and was posthumously designated the First PaN chen bla ma as a pre-incarnation of the Fourth PaN chen, Blo bzang chos kyi rgyal mtshan (1570-1662), (<https://treasuryoflives.org/biographies/view/Khedrubje-Gelek-Pelzang/8027>, accessed 12 August 2024).

¹² The *tshogs zhing* 'field of the accumulation of merit' visualizes a root guru whose lineage or religious order has originated as its main figure and who is considered fully divine. (See *Tshogs zhing: A Wall Painting in the New 'Du khang of Spituk (dPe thub)* https://www.academia.edu/9907766/Tshogs_zhing_a_wall_painting_in_the_new_Du_khang_of_Spituk_dPe_thub_pdf, accessed 31 July 2024).

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The flames of great rows of butter lamps lit the square in front of the chapel and the assembly hall, free from wind (Mkhas grub dge legs dpal bzang 2018:120-1).

Another detailed description is provided by the major Dge lugs historian Dbal mang paN+Di ta Dkon mchog rgyal mtshan (1764-1853) in his history of Lba brang Monasstery in 1800 (1987:275):

After Tsong kha pa's nirvana, his two chief students promoted new rules promoting the good deeds of Tsong kha pa, not allowing people to mourn him like laymen, and monks whose hair was longer than the width of a finger was burned with lit joss sticks. The custom of burning monks' hair continued to be practiced during the Butter Lamp Festival.

During the second year of the Butter Lamp Festival, in a significant event for the Dge lugs School, Mkhas grub dge legs dpal bzang was appointed as [Dda' ldan] monastery's disciplinarian by Rgal tshab dar ma rin chen (1364-1432). Afterward, it was a tradition for monasteries to appoint their disciplinarians during the Butter Lamp Festival, symbolizing the growth and spread of the Dge lugs School. For example, this great monastery [Bla brang] appointed its disciplinarian during the day of the *Lnga mchod* according to the tradition of Tsong kha pa's two chief students [Rgyal tshab dar ma rin chen and Mkhas grub dge legs dpal bzang]. The disciplinarian also gave a talk about discipline and instructions.

This example illustrates Dge lugs monasteries accepting, developing, and disseminating *Lnga mchod* in the TAR (Xizang), including Mdo ba Monastery. Mdo ba residents have been holding the tradition from Ra sgar's beginnings in 1915 to new monastic buildings and the monastery's reopening in the 1980s to the present.

The death of local elders and few recordings of the past have resulted in murky contemporary understandings of former times.

Certain senior monks and elders do remember what they experienced in early childhood. For example, a local senior monk provided information about Mdo ba Monastery:

On the night of the Butter Lamp Festival, local monks pitched black yak hair tents and meeting tents as their accommodation and chanting areas. Monks offered butter lamps made of flour dough. After offering the butter lamps, the monastery *dge g.yog pa* 'assistant' and abbot walked around the tents of local families to check if the herding families had offered butter lamps. Families that had offered butter lamps carried the lit *phye rkong* in a wooden basin and circumambulated their black yak hair tents and livestock. Monks scolded those who did not offer butter lamps.

At that time, *rkong bu* were too expensive for many to obtain. Consequently, some skilled locals made *rkong bu* of *sa dmar* 'red earth' and flour dough. The latter were commonly used during the night of the Butter Lamp Festival. I recall that after the reopening of our monastery, monks still made *phye rkong* and offered butter lamps in old *rkong bu* on windowsills. The disciplinarian and his two *chab ril* 'assistants' walked inside the monastery, monitoring monks offering butter lamps on their windowsills. This monitoring is known as *gling nyug* 'Tour of the Monastery'.

The locals' economic conditions gradually improved, so they bought *rkong bu* and margarine, increasing the number and variety of butter lamps offered. Butter lamps of varying sizes and patterns were offered in front of the Assembly Hall and its yard.

On the morning of the twenty-fifth day, monks paraded clockwise around the monastery's exoteric circumambulation path holding *mchod rdzas* 'offering substances'. Locals approached the monastery early in the morning and observed the monk parade known as *ser phreng*, or 'monks' procession'.

Lhag bsam offered more details:

At the very beginning, monks made a large *lha bshos* 'divine food' (see FIG. 1-1; 2;3) featuring butter colored white, yellow, blue, and red and other offering substances known as *chu gnyis nyer spyod* 'two water offerings' (FIG. 6), chanting Rje'i stong mchod 'Thousand Fold Offerings to Master Tsong kha pa'.¹³ After a while, monks wearing *chos gos* 'Dharma robes' circumambulated the Assembly Hall. With the number of monks increasing, we walked clockwise around the exoteric path of our monastery chanting *Spyan ras khros gsol* 'Cleansing Ritual of Avalokiteshvara' in the four directions.¹⁴ Ritual instruments also increased in number - parasols, victory banners, pillar hangings, peacock feather parasols, drums, cymbals, and conch shells - along with the number of monks.

In 2006, we had our new *gos sku* 'brocade Buddha image' and sunned it annually during the Butter Lamp Festival. The process of inviting Buddha images imitated Rong bo Monastery's *ser phreng* during its Great Prayer Festival. Following the monk parade, a line of benefactors carried the Buddha image on their shoulders, and monks lined up orderly (see FIG. 3). Two monks played *tsi* 'Tibetan trumpets' and slowly led the monk team. The disciplinarian's assistant held a wooden rod in his right hand and walked in front of the disciplinarian, who held a dragon-headed wooden stick for burning joss sticks. They were followed by the abbot, senior monks holding lit joss sticks, and younger monks carrying parasols. Next were victory banner holders. Another group of monks beat drums as they walked, and a monk sounded a *dung dkar g.yas* 'khyil 'right-turning white conch' while

¹³ For more see:

https://tibetanbuddhistencyclopedia.com/en/index.php?title=The_Thousand_Offerings_to_Lama_Tsongkhapa, accessed 31 July 2024.

¹⁴ They stopped at each direction of the monastery and chanted the cleansing ritual as they circumambulated the monastery.

leading a group of monks who also sounded white conches (see FIGS. 2-1;2;3).

In 2024, there were around sixty monks in Mdo ba Monastery. Ordinary locals may practice *smyung gnas* 'fasting' on this special day and visit the monastery around eight AM to watch *ser phreng*. In the following years, a large crowd of local people worshiped the Buddha image and listened to religious lectures given by the reincarnation of the founder of the local monastery, the Second Dge 'dun rgya mtsho (born in Sdong nge village in 1968; see FIG. 9), who played an important role among monks and laymen and occasionally giving religious lectures to local people. He led senior monks of Mdo ba Monastery to plan an expansion of the Mgon khang 'Protector's Hall' in 2022 and began reconstruction in 2023 with financial support from local families. There are several bronze images and four wall paintings in the new Protector's Hall, including the main figure: Rdo rje 'jigs byed 'Vajrabhairva', Dpal ldan Lha mo 'Shri Devi', Dam chen chos rgyal 'Samaya-bound Dharmaraja', Mgon po 'Mahākāla', and Rnam sras 'Vaisravana', with wall paintings of Lha mo, Dam chen chos rgyal, Mahākāla, and Vaisravana scheduled for completion in mid-2024 (see FIG.10-1;2;3;4).

After returning from the monastery, locals (mostly women) busily made *phye rkong*. However, after 2015, they mostly offered butter lamps in metal *rkong bu*. Few *phye rkong* were offered. A few families made *phye rkong* to maintain the tradition. For example, my aunt, Lcags thar skyid (b. 1970), offered butter lamps in both *phye rkong* and *rkong bu*. Lit butter lamps in basins were carried as they circumambulate their living areas, exposing the light of the butter lamps to their livestock while loudly chanting the Six Sacred Syllables and Tshong kha pa praise verses.

The following morning, *phye rkong* were baked in ashes of dry yak dung from stoves and offered to children to eat. Children

used to visit neighbors to receive *phye rkong* and brought them home to eat. My father (Chos ko, b. 1963) recalled neighbor families gave baked *phye rkong* to children who visited each of the neighbor families.

I ate baked *phye rkong* at home during my childhood in the 1990s. Images of lighting butter lamps in *phye rkong* and then eating burnt, baked *phye rkong* the next morning are memories that will never fade.

CONCLUSION

The *Lnga mchod* entails offering butter lamps to commemorate Tsong kha pa, which has been practiced in Tibetan areas for centuries. My home area, a small herding community, also observes this tradition.

If local schools gave primary school students time to celebrate local celebrations with their families, it would encourage the continuation of such traditions and help maintain a sense of community, appreciation, and understanding of cultural history.

Pad+ma+ma rig 'dzin བཤམ་མམ་རིག་འཛིན། (Wanmarenzeng 完么仁增). 2024. Lnga mchod 'Ganden Offering of the Twenty-Fifth Day' in Mdo ba (Duowa), Thun rin (Reb gong, Tongren) City, Mtho sngon (Qinghai) Province, China. *Asian Highlands Perspectives* 1-31.
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PHOTOGRAPHS

FIG. 1-1 Butter flowers (2016, Mdo ba Monastery, Rab brtan).

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FIG. 1-2 Bsod noms blo gros (b. 1999) creates butter decorations (2023, Mdo ba Monastery, Bstan 'dzin mkhyen rab).

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FIG. 1-3 Carrying divine food to the Assembly Hall (2016, Mdo ba Monastery, Rab brtan).

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FIG. 2-1 *Ser phreng*: the lead monk is *dge g.yog pa* 'disciplinarian's assistant', holding a white wood stick. The second monk is a disciplinarian who holds a dragon-headed wood stick for burning joss sticks (2016, Mdo ba Monastery, Rab gtan).

Pad+ma+ma rig 'dzin པདྨ་རྩེ་ལོ་འཛོལ། (Wanmarenzeng 完么仁增). 2024. Lnga mchod 'Ganden Offering of the Twenty-Fifth Day' in Mdo ba (Duowa), Thun rin (Reb gong, Tongren) City, Mtho sngon (Qinghai) Province, China. *Asian Highlands Perspectives* 1-31.
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FIG. 2-2 *Ser phreng*: the second and fifth monks hold *rma bya'i sgro gur* 'peacock feather parasol', and monks near the white stupa hold parasols (2016, Mdo ba Monastery, Rab gtan).

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FIG. 2-3 *Ser phreng*: the first monk holds a *tsi* 'Tibetan trumpets' (2016, Mdo ba Monastery, Rab brtan).

FIG. 3 Inviting the Buddha image (2016, Mdo ba Monastery, Rab brtan).

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FIG. 4 Sunning the Buddha (2021, Mdo ba Monastery, anonymous).

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FIG 5. Mdo ba people worship the Buddha image (2016, Mdo ba Monastery, Rab gtan).

FIG. 6 Chu gnyis nyer spyod 'two water offerings' (2022, Rong bo Monastery, Sbyin pa rgya mtsho).

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FIG. 7 *Phye skong* 'dough-ghee burners' (2021, Yo lag Village, Gcod pa 'tsho).

FIG. 8 Offering butter lamps in the Rong bo Monastery Assembly Hall yard (2021, Reb gong, Pad+ma rig 'dzin).

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FIG. 9 The temple was the first Assembly Hall after reopening the monastery in the 1980s. There was a new Assembly Hall below the temple in 2000; the old one became the Protector's Hall. The first monk holding the iron shovel was the second Dge 'dun rgya mtsho (b. 1968), and the second was Bstan 'dzin mkhyen rab (b. early 2000s); the standing monk behind the iron shovel holder is Dge bzang (b. early 2000s); the monk by the incense offering plate is Thogs med (b. 1962); and the monk standing by the concrete cart is Yig g.nyen (b. 1962). They made the ground flat to build a new incense offering (2023, Mdo ba Monastery, Bsam gtan).

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FIG.10-1 New Protection Hall (2024, Mdo ba Monastery, Pad+ma rig 'dzin).

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FIG. 10-2 Metal images in the new Protector's Hall. From left to right: Mgon po 'Mahākāla', Rdo rje 'jigs byed 'Vajrabhairva', and Dam chen chos rgyal 'Samaya-bound Dharmaraja'. Dpal ldan lha mo 'Shri Devi' was to be placed in front of the middle image in September 2024. The opening ceremony was planned for the eighth month of the Chinese lunar calendar (2024, Mdo ba Monastery, Pad+ma rig 'dzin).

Pad+ma+ma rig 'dzin པདྨ་རིག་འཛོམས། (Wanmarenzeng 完么仁增). 2024. Lnga mchod 'Ganden Offering of the Twenty-Fifth Day' in Mdo ba (Duowa), Thun rin (Reb gong, Tongren) City, Mtho sngon (Qinghai) Province, China. *Asian Highlands Perspectives* 1-31.
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FIG. 10-3 Mgon po 'Mahākāla' (2024, Mdo ba Monastery, Pad+ma rig 'dzin).

Pad+ma+ma rig 'dzin པདྨ་རིག་འཛོལ་ (Wanmarenzeng 完么仁增). 2024. Lnga mchod 'Ganden Offering of the Twenty-Fifth Day' in Mdo ba (Duowa), Thun rin (Reb gong, Tongren) City, Mtho sngon (Qinghai) Province, China. *Asian Highlands Perspectives* 1-31. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14580286

FIG. 10-4 Dam chen chos rgyal 'Samaya-bound Dharmaraja' (2024, Mdo ba Monastery, Pad+ma rig 'dzin).

Pad+ma+ma rig 'dzin པདྨ་རིག་འཛོལ་ (Wanmarenzeng 完么仁增). 2024. Lnga mchod 'Ganden Offering of the Twenty-Fifth Day' in Mdo ba (Duowa), Thun rin (Reb gong, Tongren) City, Mtho sngon (Qinghai) Province, China. *Asian Highlands Perspectives* 1-31.
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FIG. 10-5 Rje Tsong kha pa (2024, Mdo ba Monastery, Pad+ma rig 'dzin).

Pad+ma+ma rig 'dzin པདྨ་རྩེག་འཇོན། (Wanmarenzeng 完么仁增). 2024. Lnga mchod 'Ganden Offering of the Twenty-Fifth Day' in Mdo ba (Duowa), Thun rin (Reb gong, Tongren) City, Mtho sngon (Qinghai) Province, China. *Asian Highlands Perspectives* 1-31.
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FIG.10-6 Lha mo 'Shri Devi': principal Buddhist protector and main image housed in the Protection Hall (2024, Mdo ba Monastery, Lhag bsam).

Pad+ma+ma rig 'dzin བཤམ་མམ་རིག་འཛིན། (Wanmarenzeng 完么仁增). 2024. Lnga mchod 'Ganden Offering of the Twenty-Fifth Day' in Mdo ba (Duowa), Thun rin (Reb gong, Tongren) City, Mtho sngon (Qinghai) Province, China. *Asian Highlands Perspectives* 1-31. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14580286

FIG. 11-1 Khyi lnga Village sponsored the construction of the PaN chen chens shag 'Panchen's chamber' to invite the tenth PaN chen bla ma to Mdo ba Monastery. Construction was completed in 1990 after the PaN chen passed away. The building in the picture was rebuilt around 2010 (2024, Mdo ba Monastery, Pad+ma rig 'dzin).

Pad+ma+ma rig 'dzin པད་མ་མ་རིག་འཛིན། (Wanmarenzeng 完么仁增). 2024. Lnga mchod 'Ganden Offering of the Twenty-Fifth Day' in Mdo ba (Duowa), Thun rin (Reb gong, Tongren) City, Mtho sngon (Qinghai) Province, China. *Asian Highlands Perspectives* 1-31. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14580286

FIG. 11-2 The Nang chen courtyard (2024, Mdo ba Monastery, Pad+ma rig 'dzin).

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'du khang འདུ་ཁང།
 bka' 'gyur བཀའ་འགྲུལ།
 bka' gdams བཀའ་གདམས།
 bka' rgyud བཀའ་རྒྱུད།
 bla brang ལྗ་བང།
 blo bzang chos kyi rgyal
 mtshan ལྗོ་བཟང་ཚོས་གྱི་རྒྱལ་མཚན།
 brtson 'grus བརྩོན་འགྲུལ།
 bsod nams blo gros
 བསོད་ནམས་ལྗོ་གྲོས།
 bstan 'dzin mkhyen rab བསྐྱེན་
 འཛིན་མཁྱེན་རབ།

bstan 'gyur བསྐྱེན་འགྲུལ།
 btson 'grus བརྩོན་འགྲུལ།
 chab ril ཆབ་རིལ།
 chos gos ཚོས་གོས།
 chu gnyis nyer spyod
 ལྷ་གཉིས་ཉེར་སྤྱོད།
 dam chen chos rgyal དམ་ཆེན་ཚོས་རྒྱ།
 dga' ldan khri pa དགའ་ལྗན་ཁི་པ།
 dga' ldan lnga mchod;
 Ganden Ngamchoe དགའ་ལྗན་ལྗ་མཚོ།
 dge 'dun rgya mtsho དགེ་འདུན་རྒྱ་མཚོ།
 dge bshes དགེ་བཤེས།

dge bzang དགེ་བཟང་།
dge g.yog pa དགེ་གཡོག་པ།
dge lugs དགེ་ལུགས།
dngul rkong དངུལ་རྫོང་།
dung dkar g.yas 'khyil

དུང་དཀར་གཡམ་འཕྱིལ།

gcod le གཙོང་ལེ།
gcod pa 'tsho གཙོང་པ་འཚོ།
gling nyug གླིང་ལུག
gos sku གོས་སུ།
gyan གྲན།
gzims shag གཟིམས་ཤག
kha skya ཀ་སྐལ།
khyi rnga ཀྱི་རྩ།
klad rko ཀླང་རྫོ།
lam rim tshogs zhing

ལམ་རིམ་ཚོགས་ཤིང་།

lcags thar skyid ལྷགས་ཐར་སྐྱིད།
lha bshos ལྷ་བཤོས།
lha mo ལྷ་མོ།
mchod rkong མཚོང་རྫོང་།
mdo ba མདོ་བ།
mdo ba 'brog dgon pa
མདོ་བ་འབྲོག་དགོན་པ།
mdo sngags dar rgyas gling
མདོ་སྲགས་དར་རྒྱས་གླིང་།
mgon po མགོན་པོ།
mkhas grub dge legs dpal
bzang; Khedrup Rinpoche
མཁས་གྲུབ་དགེ་ལེགས་དཔལ་བཟང་།
mtsho sngon མཚོ་ཕྱོན།
nang chen ནང་ཆེན།
paN chen bla ma པཎ་ཆེན་བླ་མ།

phye rkong ཕྱེ་རྫོང་།
rab brtan རབ་བརྟན།
rdo rje 'jigs byed རྩེ་འཇིགས་བྱེད།
reb gong རེབ་རྫོང་།
rgyal tshab dar ma rin chen

རྒྱལ་ཚབ་དར་མ་རིན་ཆེན།

rkang rjen sman pa ཀང་རྩེན་སྐྱབ་པ།
rkong bu རྫོང་བུ།
rma bya'i sgro gur ར་བྱའི་སྐྱོ་གུར།
rma lho ར་ལྷོ།
rnam sras རྣམ་སྲས།
rtse khog རྩེ་ཁོག
sa skya ས་སྐལ།
sbyin pa rgya mtsho སྐྱིན་པ་རྒྱ་མཚོ།
sdong nge སོང་ངེ།
ser phreng སེར་ཕྲེང་།
sgrol dkar སྐྱོལ་དཀར།
sman sku སྐྱབ་སུ།
sman tog སྐྱབ་ཏོག
smyung gnas སྐྱུང་གནས།
spyen ras khurus gsol
སྐྱུན་རས་ལུས་གསོལ།
sti སྐ།
thogs med ཐོགས་མེད།
tshe dpa' ཚེ་དཔལ།
tsong kha pa ཚོང་ཀ་པ།
thun rin ཐུན་རིན།
lhag bsam ལྷག་བསམ།
rong bo རོང་བོ།
wa gor ས་གོར།
dbyig gnyen དབྱིག་གཉེན།
zangs rkong ཟངས་རྫོང་།
zhwa gon ལྷ་གོན།

Pad+ma+ma rig 'dzin པད་མམ་མམ་རིག་འཛིན། (Wanmarenzeng 完么仁增). 2024. Lnga mchod 'Ganden Offering of the Twenty-Fifth Day' in Mdo ba (Duowa), Thun rin (Reb gong, Tongren) City, Mtho sngon (Qinghai) Province, China. *Asian Highlands Perspectives* 1-31.
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CHINESE TERMS

Duowa 多哇

Gansu 甘肃

Huangnan 黄南

mu 亩

Qinghai 青海

Randeng jie 燃灯节

Tongren 同仁

Xiahe 夏河

Zeku 泽库